

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OJIGHO****FIRST NAME: OSAI****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used the following software: MS Word 365 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Organising and planning essays (EUCLID 2021, 6-14)
2. Understanding punctuation rules (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Appropriate use of American or UK English (EUCLID 2021, 23, 25-32)
4. Adapting a style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Combatting plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAYS

1) INTRODUCTION

I was elated when I applied and was accepted for the Doctorate in International Law and Treaty Law (DILT). I expected to be involved in writing many essays and was prepared to tackle areas of interest early on. I, therefore, welcomed the opportunity to study the international academic writing course but was slightly taken aback by how comprehensive it was.

I have read the ACA-401D course pack a few times and viewed the accompanying video, which provides an overview of how to write an academic essay by incorporating tips for enhancing writing, learning proper and acceptable use of punctuation, encouraging consistent use of language by choosing one World English variant and using style guides generally and the Chicago Turabian style more specifically to format and present papers that meet international standards.

In this response paper, I reviewed the process of organising and planning essays, punctuation, considerations for choosing British English over American English, use of style guides and combatting plagiarism. I also used the Zotero app to help with my citations and Grammarly to edit my work.

2) ORGANISING AND PLANNING ESSAYS

Academic essays are structured pieces of writing. I understand it is advisable to start developing them early to have adequate time to organise my thoughts, collect the needed materials and complete the writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14). I have written several essays and papers as part of my work. Still, I found that concerning an academic essay, I need to go beyond describing the idea or issue I am writing about to analyse and present the findings of my enquiry (EUCLID 2021, 7). The analysis stands out in academic writing, which showcases something new to readers or provides a different perspective on existing knowledge. (Wilson 2022, 14-15).

It helps to follow some steps in organising and planning the essays. Every essay answers a question or set of questions or explores an issue. This is the foundation on which the essay is developed. The first step, therefore, is to identify what you want to know or write about and clarify it by analysing what is required to achieve that. Then, research the topic, noting essential information. Next, organise ideas and have an outline of the content of the essay. The following steps involve writing the essay following the plan, referencing accurately to acknowledge sources, editing and re-working the draft, and seeking reviews from colleagues to improve the essay. I noted that leaving a draft for a few days is good practice, followed by revisiting it to gain new insights that can strengthen the essay's arguments. The final step is submitting the essay by the deadline (EUCLID 2021, 8-12).

3) UNDERSTANDING PUNCTUATION RULES

A key objective of writing is to communicate. All essays would, therefore, benefit from using punctuation correctly so that the message is understood clearly. Understanding the correct usage of apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons and semi-colons, commas, full stops, and other punctuation marks would improve the writing (EUCLID 2021, 16-23). I discovered that brackets can be used to provide additional information about a sentence preceding it. However, one must be careful where the full stops and other punctuations are placed. For example, punctuations are placed after the closing brackets, but the full stop or other punctuation is placed before the closing brackets where a complete sentence is in the brackets. I also noted that there are different brackets: round, square, angle, or curly, and they are used for specific purposes (EUCLID 2021, 17).

When using bullet points to list items, I usually put a full stop at the end of each item. I discovered that this is generally incorrect except in two cases. The first is when the bullet points are part of a sentence or contain texts that are complete sentences themselves, requiring punctuation for logical flow (EUCLID 2021, 18). Interestingly, no permissible cases exist for using the m-dash compared to the n-dash and the hyphen (EUCLID 2021, 20).

4) APPROPRIATE USE OF AMERICAN OR UK ENGLISH

Standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE), also called UK English, are the dominant World English variants (EUCLID 2021, 25). While it appears that SAE is more prevalent due to a larger population of American users and other factors, such as the massive number of American universities compared to British ones, I would challenge this. The notion of dominance may be skewed because it did not consider other regions like India and English-speaking Africa, where British English is more likely to be the dominant English variant due to historical colonial ties to those regions (EUCLID 2021, 25).

The choice to use one variant over the other is a personal preference. I have chosen UK English because I have written in this language variant for most of my life, and I relate more with UK-based institutions than US organisations. Moreover, EUCLID permits students to use either variant of English, provided it is consistently applied (Euclid 2021, 25). I appreciate both the similarities and differences of each variant, mainly around the spelling of certain words, for example, cheque (i.e., UK English), v check (i.e., American English), and the use of quotation marks in presenting reported speech, which I would put into practice (EUCLID 2021, 25-32).

5) ADOPTING A STYLE GUIDE

A style guide offers a writer a uniform format incorporating certain elements to make the writing distinguishable for the field of work it relates to (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). According to Wilson, the style in which a paper is written can, on the face of it, show the reader whether it is a scientific one because papers written using APA style are often empirical ones. In contrast, those written for the humanities adopt other styles such as Chicago and MLA in addition to APA. I was impressed to learn that style guides are more than just about language and punctuation. They can contain elements that consider audience segmentation, length of submission, and branding (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

Style guides are valuable tools that, in the long term, help me write consistently and prepare my work for publication. I found that many publishers have a style, and if I wish to contribute to their journals, I must abide by their rules by identifying their preferred style guide and complying with it (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). I noted that the Chicago Turabian style is straightforward to apply.

6) COMBATTING PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism occurs when a writer passes off the work of another as theirs or without attributing accurately the source of ideas, quotes, and other material in their finished work. Plagiarism is unacceptable, and everyone must strive to avoid it by citing all sources of information (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Text taken from a source can be presented as quotations in an essay and attributed to the author by placing it in quotation marks with the author's name and the appropriate page number of the publication in brackets. However, copious use of quotations is not advised as this defeats the purpose of producing an academic paper of the writer's intellectual work and can inadvertently lead to plagiarism. A rule of thumb is to use quotations sparingly and paraphrase using your own words instead. Depending on the publication style, sources can be cited as in-text citations, a list of works or a combination of both (EUCLID 2021, 35-39). The most important thing is to check that all material used in developing the essay has been appropriately cited.

7) CONCLUSION

I have found the first period of the course very informative through the easy-to-read sections in the course pack and interactive tools, such as Zotero, that I was introduced to. I got an in-depth refresher on the building blocks of an essay, which increased my knowledge of what is required to produce an academic essay of high quality. Before, I had not paid much attention to the time I set aside at the initial stage of developing a paper. I agree that dedicating enough time to planning, including composing and organising my thoughts, is crucial for the writing process to flow systematically.

It was also evident that I would need to refer to the punctuation guides regularly as I develop my writing to apply them appropriately during my studies. While the arguments around the dominant use of American English over British English were impressive, I am grateful that I can use the variant I am most familiar with and comfortable with. I am already a fan of style guides, so I would make the most of the various guidelines as required. A recurring mention as I read the course pack was plagiarism and why it was crucial to avoid it as it carried significant consequences that attacked the research integrity. This is one area that calls for greater vigilance and consciousness. I intend to improve my citation and paraphrasing skills and use tools such as Grammarly to assist in flagging areas for improvement.

Overall, I recommend that all postgraduate students take the International academic writing course because it does set the foundation for better writing.

REFERENCES

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Wilson, Jeffrey. 2022. *Academic Writing*. Accessed December 14, 2023. <https://wilson.fas.harvard.edu/AcademicWriting>.

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